

MS.3 Tools to evaluate networking and knowledge exchange

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Means of Verification

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1. Introduction

This document gives an overview of the strategy, methods and tools that will be used in the project to evaluate networking, knowledge exchange and capacity building on CSF. The evaluation will serve 3 objectives:

1. To update the guidelines for knowledge exchange and capacity building generated in Tasks 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4 and to make sure that the processes in the project work for everybody.
2. To feed the capacity building in Task 1.5
3. To develop recommendations regarding networking, knowledge exchange and capacity building on CSF for wider dissemination through WP2 (tasks 2.4 and 2.5) and WP8.

In the first years, the evaluation will focus on the streamlining and optimizing the guidelines and processes of knowledge exchange within the network and project and to capture the training needs. Later on, when the processes are clear and functional for everybody, the focus will shift more towards the development of lessons learned and recommendations and capacity building materials.

Based on the conceptual framework developed in Deliverable 1.1, we envision the monitoring and evaluation of activities to take place on multiple levels:

- The level of the PDF
- The national level (incl. living labs if relevant)
- The EU/thematic level

Evaluation tools will be adapted along the project, depending on lessons learned and new insights from previous evaluation cycles. The following timeline will be repeated every year:

Figure 1. Yearly evaluation and adaptation rationale

2. Evaluation of the guidelines and knowledge exchange processes

2.1 Aim

The main question we would like to answer with this set of evaluation tools is: *How can the produced guidelines for knowledge exchange within the network be optimized in a way they work for network members as well as keep meeting the project objectives?*

In the first year of the project, guidelines for knowledge exchange were developed in Milestone 1 “Guidelines for national and EU knowledge exchange” and Deliverable 3.1 “Guidelines for Climate Smart Farming demonstration activities and campaigns”. Every year, these guidelines will be updated based on an evaluation performed by the network participants on different levels. The evaluation will be focussed on the knowledge exchange processes within the project. Since often unforeseen practical implications related to the implementation of guidelines are overlooked, this will probably be mostly relevant in the first years. Experiences in the NEFERTITI project have shown that it takes 1-2 years for the network members to incorporate and adopt the guidelines in a way that they work and become an added value in their own context. Only once these guidelines are incorporated in the network, they start resulting in fruitful outcomes and lessons learned (and thus contributing to objectives 2 and 3 mentioned in the introduction).

2.2 Framework

In the D1.1 Conceptual framework for knowledge exchange, we introduced the concept of boundary spaces and boundary activities between different levels in the project. It is through the boundary activities that knowledge can circulate through the network. This stresses the importance of evaluating and recognizing the barriers within these knowledge exchange processes.

Figure 2. Knowledge creation levels within Climate Farm Demo (introduced in D1.1)

2.3 Evaluation tools

2.3.1 During GA meetings

Each year during April and May, WP1 will develop process evaluation tools, that will allow to evaluate the knowledge exchange barriers and other structural barrier within the network and project. The Mid-Term annual meetings (MTAM) are an interesting period to perform this first assessment, because is if gives ExCom the opportunity to adapt the guidelines for the network based on the worries and barriers expressed by the in-person annual meeting in September/October. These updated guidelines can then be presented and discussed during the in-person annual meeting and taken home to the national and thematic networks for implementation.

Depending on the time available during the MTAM evaluation questions either will be send by survey before or will be discussed in break out groups during the MTAM. Participants will be asked in general:

- What goes well in the network?
- What did not go well in the network?
- Is their role in the network clear?
- What should be changed?
- Do they miss something?
- How to they perceive the connection between the ExCom and the network through the NMU?
- How can the project support them better?

During the MTAM, in break out sessions, participants will be asked to reflect on Figure 2, what goes well in the boundary spaces, and what goes wrong. In this way we aim to achieve an insight in the barriers for knowledge flows within the network.

2.3.2 During NMU and TL meeting

During NMU and TL meetings, an evaluation of the KE in national and thematic networks will be made.

3. Evaluation of the capacity building

3.1 Level of the PDFs

Learning question we would like to answer:

How do the knowledge exchange activities organised in the project contribute to the behaviour change of farmers towards climate smart farming?

Aim:

All PDFs will be audited on their climate impact in the beginning and end of the project. However behaviour change or the adoption of practices involves different phases, of which the measurable change in climate impact is only the very final phase. Moreover, the behaviour change phase PDFs are in, also will impact the type of advice and support they need. To gain insights in the progression of PDFs, we would like to add some additional questions to the audit, to capture the phase they are in and to provide additional question to support the CFAs in helping to draft the adaptation and mitigation plans (AMPs) of the PDFs. This will help us and the CFAs understand the farmers' attitudes, willingness etc. to change specific practices.

Tools for evaluation:

In the audit and adaptation and mitigation plan (AMP):

An additional tab page is added with questions to probe for the farmers attitude, willingness and progress on the implementation of climate smart farming. Based on this interview, the CFA is asked to give scores for the individual PDFS on the different stages of the ADKAR model.

Questions for the farmer	Answer
What is your motivation to participate in the project?	<i>Should we have pre-set answers?</i>
How climate smart would you estimate your farm on a scale from 1 (not climate smart at all) to 10 (very climate smart)?	

According to you, what are your farm's strengths for dealing with the effects of climate change and for lowering your businesses impact on climate change?	
According to you, what are your farm's weaknesses for dealing with the effects of climate change and for lowering its effect on climate change?	
Can you list some points of improvement to make your farm more climate smart?	<p>Crop rotation</p> <p>Managing food resource livestock</p> <p>Managing water resource</p> <p>Increasing water resource</p> <p>Adapting livestock management</p> <p>Improving soil properties</p> <p>Soil covering</p> <p>Implementing agroecological infrastructures</p> <p>Optimizing perennial crops management</p> <p>Cultivating under cover (greenhouse or PV panels)</p> <p>Adapting feeding and watering</p> <p>Protecting animals from heat</p> <p>Energy Management</p>
Do you know which measures you could take to make advancement on the abovementioned points for improvement?	
In your opinion, what do you need (from your advisor) to implement the abovementioned measures?	
In your opinion, what do you need to sustain the already implemented climate measures?	
Questions for the advisor after the conversation with the farmer	Score 1-5 (with 1= not at all - 5= very much)
How aware do you consider the farmer about the need to become more climate smart?	
Does the farmer express a clear desire to become climate smart?	
Does the farmer have the skills and knowledge to successfully implement the required changes?	
Does the farmer have the ability, support and means to implement the required changes?	
Is the farmer able to maintain already implemented changes?	

This evaluation will be repeated every year when the action plan is evaluated. In addition, the following questions will be asked:

How did past year's project activities support you in making the change:

- The project activities increased my awareness on [key topic]: Scale 1-7
- The project activities increased my desire to change practices on my farm: scale 1-7
- The project activities increased my knowledge and skills on how to make my farm more climate smart: Scale 1-7
- The project activities increased my ability to implement climate smart practices by providing me access tools, procedures, networks, means ...: scale 1-7
- The project activities helped me to sustain earlier implemented climate smart practices: scale 1-7

These evaluations will provide us figures for 1500 PDFs across the EU and will provide insights on where the PDF's behaviour change needs are in each country. Such an overview will help us to select case studies for further in-depth and qualitative evaluation. Preferably, one case study is selected for each stage in the ADKAR model.

3.2 At national level

At the national annual meeting, national networks are asked to discuss the priority topics for climate smart farming for their country. PDFs and CFAs present will be asked where they are for this topic on the ADKAR scale.

For each defined priority topic they must give a score for each stage in the ADKAR model. This should be included in the script for the annual meetings. These scores will serve as a basis to define the strategies for support and activities at national level (give priority to all scores of 3 and below) and what the focus of the knowledge exchange activities (and broader in the AKIS) should be. These evaluations will be repeated every year during the national annual meetings. The results of this group evaluation process will provide insights to the national network on the activities within the AKIS that require most attention.

	Behaviour change phase	Score (1-5)
A	Awareness: How aware are the farmers of the need to change? Do the farmers understand the need for change? (1= not aware at all – 5= very aware)	
D	Desire: Do the farmers have a clear desire to change?	

	(1= no desire at all – 5= very high desire to change)	
K	<p>Knowledge: Do the farmers have the skills and knowledge to successfully implement the change?</p> <p>(1= knowledge is completely absent – 5= knows perfectly how to start the change)</p>	
A	<p>Ability: Do the farmers have the ability, support and means to change?</p> <p>(1= ability, support and means are totally absent – 5= PDF is able to invest time, means and effort in the change)</p>	
R	<p>Reinforcement: Are the farmers able to maintain the change?</p> <p>(1= PDF has negative experiences with the implemented change – 5= Farmer feels successful and supported by its context after implementing the change.</p>	

At the end of year2, national networks will also be asked to evaluate their knowledge exchange activities in relation to the ADKAR score that they gave in the previous year and the current year.

Feedback on the evaluation of demo events
Please provide here the answers in English based on the completed ME&L tool as described in the guidelines

Demo year highlights	
Main challenges in demonstrating climate smart farming	
Demo example(s) from your climate issue	
Suggested improvements in demo organisations for the coming year	
(Project) support needed to improve the CSF demos?	

Feedback on the evaluation of other knowledge exchange activities
Please provide here the answers in English based on the completed ME&L tool as described in the guidelines

Description of successful knowledge exchange activities in the national network (that were not demo events) last year. How did they contribute to solving the barriers in the ADKAR evaluation.	
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Which (type of) knowledge exchange activities were missed in the national network last year	
Suggestions for future national activities	

3.3 At thematic level

Each year thematic networks (under the lead of the Thematic leader) will have to make a knowledge exchange plan. For this they will evaluate the status of the knowledge on their thematic area, select priority topics, and draft their agenda.

In this plan, they will have to reflect on the status of the priority topics on the ADKAR model.

	Behaviour change phase	Farmers Score (1-5)	Advisors Score (1-5)
A	Awareness: How aware are the farmers/advisors of the need to change? Do the farmers/advisors understand the need for change? (1= not aware at all – 5= very aware)		
D	Desire: Do the farmers/advisors have a clear desire to change? (1= no desire at all – 5= very high desire to change)		
K	Knowledge: Do the farmers/advisors have the skills and knowledge to successfully implement the change? (1= knowledge is completely absent – 5= knows perfectly how to start the change)		
A	Ability: Do the farmers/advisors have the ability, support and means to change?		

	(1= ability, support and means are totally absent – 5= PDF is able to invest time, means and effort in the change)		
R	<p>Reinforcement: Are the farmers/advisors able to maintain the change?</p> <p>(1= PDF has negative experiences with the implemented change – 5= Farmer feels successful and supported by its context after implementing the change.</p>		

3.4 Case studies

The outputs of the ADKAR surveys on each level will contribute to the selection of cases. A case could be a country, a priority topic or a thematic area. The case study will try to answer the questions:

- how did the project activities contribute to the farmers’ needs (based on where they are in the ADKAR model),
- What exactly in these activities made it contribute to the ADKAR behaviour change process?

A case study approach will be further developed by the end of year 2 in the project, once the cases are defined. Most likely it will include interviews and focus groups with CFA, NCs, and if possible farmers. It relevant, a survey might be organized amongst the case study participants prior to the interviews and focus groups, to allow a more targeted preparation of the interview and focus group guides.

A selection of case studies will be done every 2 years and a specific approach will be developed to retrieve the specific information. Preferably there is minimally 1 case for each step in the ADKAR process, so we can retrieve insights in the activities that are organised to support farmers in each phase of the ADKAR model.

National Knowledge Exchange Plan #[Add number]

Country:

Date: [add date of submission]

National Coordinator: [Name, Organisation]

CFA contributors: [Names]

Objective

The objective of the knowledge exchange plan is to provide a structured approach to develop activities that serve the national Climate Farm Demo networks. It helps to specify the networks' goals and to plan related activities to reach these goals. It helps to align all knowledge exchange and capacity building activities in a country and to work towards shared objectives. This document can then be used to monitor and evaluate the activities in organised in the national network.

The plans result from the discussion organised during annual meetings and monitoring of activities on the CFD website [back-office dashboard](#), to be integrated in this template. They will have to be update yearly and submitted by December of each working year, from 2023 onwards.

Climate impact

Describe here the current situation regarding climate change in your country based on the discussion during the national kick off meeting.

- *What does climate change mean in your country? What is the impact for farmers and how do agricultural activities impact climate change?*
- *What are or will be the main challenges in your country?*
- *Think about how you could link the CFD activities to other activities in your country.*

Answer:

Priority topics identified:

Existing expertise and initiatives

- *Which projects, initiatives, trainings, resources etc. do already exist in our country that are dealing with these topics?*
- *How could the CFD national network activities link and create synergies with these?_*
- *What would be the knowledge needs of the farmers, advisors and other AKIS actors that your network activities could fill?*

Answer:

Where would you estimate the farmers in your country/region locate themselves in the adoption process regarding the topics put forward? Mark the stages that are most applicable for each priority topic. Repeat this for each priority topic defined.

PRIORITY TOPIC: [Add here the priority topic]		
Stage in behaviour change process of target audience		Support need of farmers on this topic
1.	Farmers are not yet acknowledging a problem	Building awareness on the effects of climate change and climate policy related to the topic. Making them aware about the importance to change the practices Gaining insights in the opportunities related to this topic. communicate the importance of change
2.	Farmers acknowledge there is a problem, but are not yet ready to change	Farmer need to be made aware about what is in it for them. Farmers need to link the potential actions to their personal motivators
3.	Farmers are getting ready to change	They need demonstrations on the different climate solutions and research innovations. They need support in deciding on the right adaptation and mitigation measures for their farms. Farmers need training and need to develop skills on specific adaptation and mitigation measures
4.	Farmers are testing adaptation and mitigation measures	Farmers need to share experiences with peers Farmers should co-create knowledge on specific climate issues and adaptation and mitigation measures. Farmers should be trained on how to implement climate policy and regulations
5	Farmers are trying to maintain and grow the new behaviour	Farmers need to be networked to farmers and other actors, to strengthen cooperation and partnerships. Farmers need to debrief lessons learned.

	Priority topic: [add here the priority topic]	Score (1-5)
A	Awareness: How aware are the farmers of the need to change? Do the farmers understand the need for change? (1= not aware at all – 5= very aware)	
D	Desire: Do the farmers have a clear desire to change? (1= no desire at all – 5= very high desire to change)	
K	Knowledge: Do the farmers have the skills and knowledge to successfully implement the change? (1= knowledge is completely absent – 5= knows perfectly how to start the change)	
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R	Reinforcement: Are the farmers able to maintain the change? (1= PDF has negative experiences with the implemented change – 5= Farmer feels successful and supported by its context after implementing the change.	

Goals & Strategies

Given the situation outlined above, think about what you want to achieve with your national CFD network in the coming year and what strategies you can use to achieve them. Specify the objectives, potential strategies (e.g. abovementioned initiatives to link with), the target groups, other actors to involve for the priority topics selected.

Based on the strategies revealed mentioned above provide a specific knowledge exchange action plan / program to be implemented for the next annual period. Include different kinds of activities such as demo events, trainings, workshops, national meetings, ... depending on the objectives and target group.

	Priority topic	Activity type <i>(demo event, national meeting, cross visit, training, capacity building, workshop, ...)</i>	Main objective of the event (+link to awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, reinforcement)	Target group	Most suitable period	Potential location	Person / organization responsible for organization
1.							
2.							
3.							
...							

Challenges

Which challenges do you identify in the implementation of these strategies and how could they be anticipated?

Answer:

Evaluation of the national network activities

In the case of the first National Annual Meeting, this point is not relevant

The yearly activities will be evaluated on annual national meetings, and using feedback, the knowledge exchange plans will be refined for the following years. From 2024 onwards first perform the evaluation of the activities before adapting the national knowledge exchange plan.

Feedback on the evaluation of demo events

Please provide here the answers in English based on the completed ME&L tool as described in the guidelines

Demo year highlights	
Main challenges in demonstrating climate smart farming	
Demo example(s) from your climate issue	
Suggested improvements in demo organisations for the coming year	
(Project) support needed to improve the CSF demos?	

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Description of successful knowledge exchange activities in the national network (that were not demo events) last year	
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